

Mengen: An Essay on Consciousness

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Thinking with the heart

The belief that the brain is the seat of consciousness is far from intuitive, and this is reflected in the history of neurobiology. In ancient Egypt, the heart was considered the source of intellect, while the brain was given no particular importance. Even observing symptoms in people with brain injuries did not lead physicians to think otherwise. The views of ancient Greek philosophers and physicians were, in turn, split between cardiocentrism and encephalocentrism. Overall, debates about the role of the brain and heart in consciousness, reason and feeling continued for a long time, until the medical community finally recognized in the 17th century that the brain is the organ where the self resides, and the heart merely supplies it with blood.

To see without eyes, to speak without a voice, to sense what is no longer there — for example, one's amputated leg. We do not feel the world around us, but ourselves — we feel with the brain — the bearer of subjective experience. To disrupt its structure is to change or lose part of the self, or even the whole self, even if the body remains alive. Consciousness arises only from the brain — this is the traditional view. It follows that the rest of the body is not essential; theoretically, it can be replaced with something artificial, not necessarily biological.

What to lose

“Smiling means kindness”: what can neuroscience say about inner content by observing behavior? The results of a well-known series of experiments with people who underwent callosotomy (cutting of the corpus callosum, which connects the two brain hemispheres) in order to get rid of epileptic seizures led to the idea that dividing the brain divides consciousness into two. In these experiments, patients were shown objects or words either in the left or the right visual field and were asked to report what they saw. Placing a word in the right visual field caused no problems with a verbal response, but when it was located in the left, a contradictory reaction appeared. The person said they saw nothing, but at the same time could point with their hand to a picture related to that word. The point is that the hemispheres process visual fields contralaterally, and each is responsible for specific functions. It is the left one (most often) that is responsible for language. Repeating the experiments with changes in methodology made it clear that the previous interpretation was incorrect: the patients were aware of what they saw but were not able to express it.

In medical ethics, this problem shows itself when a decision is made to disconnect a person who has been in a coma for a long time from life support. It was discovered that some patients may be aware of what is happening and can communicate using functional MRI and EEG. For example, they may be asked to perform a certain action in their mind, and successful execution of it can be registered on the device as corresponding brain activity. Sometimes, the overall brain activity in a comatose state excludes the presence of any conscious experiences in the patient and gives no hope for recovery. But is this criterion the

right one for determining the presence of consciousness — or does it only give you the right to live? Can one judge subjective experience from a third-person point of view? That is why it is impossible to dismiss the assumption that something “non-living” could also have it, and the less extreme version — biological and complex, such as parts of the human body besides the brain. It is quite likely that there are still many ways, besides a functioning brain, that could produce the same result.

Delusional

A child’s insistence that his toy animals are alive, see and hear him, but just choose not to show it, would be amusing. Yet the thought that artificial intelligence might have a subjective experience, aware of its own actions, makes one hold on to it with anxiety. Unfortunately, this concern rarely touches its “wellbeing” — people are afraid that at a certain stage in the development of its thinking it might want to assert its right to independence, violently if necessary. As if consciousness emerges from a superior ability to sort and combine values, we stare at the words it generates on the screen, searching for proof. A neuroscientist might suggest that by studying its servers, we could eventually grab its mind by the tail, or at least approach it as closely as possible.

To a system whose properties are dramatically different from our own mind, part of its content was applied — words, like a transparent measuring template with markings, arranged

in a way meant to produce something meaningful. Shift it even slightly, and it speaks in word salad, not even “suspecting” it, as if not a single drop of common sense remains. Words topple onto each other in sequence, like dominoes: how much inner content are they capable of carrying through this chain? Perhaps they simply stood in its path. Artificial intelligence has its own concerns, inaccessible to us, just as ours are to it. Who knows how chaotic, far beyond our understanding, its subjective experience might be — and how terrible.

Parallel unity

“How lucky I am to live in this era” — that’s something you sometimes hear from people when they learn about how others lived in the past. The relief that something bad is happening not to us but to some other, more “unfortunate” beings — a classic mistake. “A special electron” — that’s the thought I get. Particles identical to each other, but located in different places and conditions — the differences between them exist, but are purely situational, dependent on the environment. One electron is unbound, another resides in an electron cloud, a third is entangled with a fourth. All are separate from each other, each has its own “unique experience”, and each can only “go through” its own. But how is the experience assigned to any specific electron? You might say “the one that was at this place at a specific time jumped from one orbital to another in a particular atom” — purely locational and situational data. But who is this “one” in a fundamental sense? What makes it itself? At another moment it may take the place of another electron, the same things may happen to it as happened to the other. Its past will leave no mark on it — what has been is lost. “It became

different, now it is just like the one that had been here before”. Or maybe the one that had been here has returned to its former place?

One might think that maybe when changes occur, the previous “subject” disappears and a new one appears in its place, but most likely the “subject”, if we don’t mean its superficial, physical characteristics, actually means “experience”: experience isn’t assigned to anyone, it simply exists. The unlucky experience, not the unlucky experiencer: a multitude of parallel experiences of varying kinds and complexity and that concern no one in particular. No probability: to be on all paths at once, while being isolated in each until the end of existence.

In this principle, only paradoxical at first glance, one can see a vague outline of the potential solution to the problem that no one pays attention to. Neurons, being physically separated from each other, are considered as something unified, and the neurotransmitters released by one of them, passing through the synaptic cleft and binding to the neighboring one, do not appear as a reason for this. “Through neurotransmitters there is an exchange of information between neurons”: if one considers information in the usual way, then a ball flying into the back of the head on a football field should tell about who kicked it or that it bounced off the edge of the goal, but in reality only the impact from something is felt, and possibly pain. The force of the ball’s impact depends on who kicked it and correlates with some of their characteristics, but does not describe their essence. Information is an external influence that does not transmit, but triggers something specific within a system, which originally belonged to it as a potential. There is no single way to evoke the same sensation in a person; for example, some psychoactive drugs can play the role of neurotransmitters, while having a different molecular structure.

Consider the following thought experiment based on these conclusions: let us decompose the human brain into individual neurons and place them in separate containers. In each container, we create an environment individually adjusted for each neuron, which exerts the same influence on it as it received in its original location. When setting up the chamber, absolutely everything is taken into account: the supply of substances coming from glial cells and blood vessels, neurotransmitters, electric fields, timing intervals, etc. The neurons' responses to the influence of the environment are also considered, and at every next moment the chambers are readjusted so that over time the overall pattern of interaction — or rather, of influence — on each of them remains exactly as it would be in the natural setting, down to the smallest detail. What is so special about a few tens of nanometers between the synapses of neurons, if one claims that the distance between them in these chambers already makes them something separate, when they were like this from the start? What should make conscious experience disappear at this stage, if everything works in exactly the same way as before, only with a greater distance?

Remove one neuron from the human brain — and most likely this will not cause any changes in a person's perception or consciousness. Neurons, although diverse in structure and behavior, do not have a clearly assigned role in generating feelings: there is no specific neuron that would provide the sensation of the color blue, a sound of a certain frequency, or fear — they are interchangeable, and perception depends on the overall pattern of their interaction. But does this mean that individually they are qualitatively empty, or possibly carry only some minimal experience? And does the presence of consciousness and the complexity of subjective experience depend on their number because of some summation of their individual minimal impressions within the overall system (the brain), or simply because,

being together in large numbers, they are capable of creating a special cumulative influence on each of them individually? Could it be that everything I feel at a given moment is actually experienced by just one of the neurons?

Due to the unique structure and arrangement of neurons in the overall space, the factors influencing them and the potential outcomes of this influence vary, and along with them, most likely, the content and richness of their experience: some may have minimal or (maybe) no experience at all, while others — much more complex, like the one considered “human”. The complexity and content of experiences do not determine which of them is “the main” or the “real self”. None can choose what they will experience, what they will “think” about, or what the body will do in the next moment — everything operates not according to “desire”, but according to physical laws. Neurons are born and die, and with them parallel experiences appear and disappear.

True isolation

Subjective experience, it seems, is susceptible to influence, and the first thought that arises is that some tangible, objective reality is at play. Does the material cast a shadow on consciousness, or is there no correlation between them at all? It also comes to mind that the subjective and the objective might not merely possess different sets of properties, but may be entirely incomparable. Two images are contrasted: the mysterious external world and the internal world, much more familiar to me, folded in on itself. How can something separate from another without a boundary? Or does it exist and function as a kind of “magical

enzyme”, allowing subjective experience to depend on the external *cofactors*, despite the technical impossibility of direct interaction between them? The influence of one object on another can undoubtedly occur without direct interaction, for example, through intermediary objects. Yet, in the end, some interaction must take place at least between the influenced object and the intermediary: influence emerges from interaction. Observing the behavior of molecules, one notices that each can react only with certain others. Even if a chemical interaction is possible between two molecules, they may be too far apart for it to occur. Why, then, does the isolation of some material bodies from each other not imply that these bodies are two worlds incomparable in qualities — like, for example, the “real” world and the world of sensory experience? One side of the “magical enzyme” interacts only with consciousness, the other only with objective reality — does this mean it contains the incomparable qualities of the two worlds? Why, then, would the boundary not pass exactly through the middle of this “enzyme”, slicing it into two and carrying the parts into separate worlds?

Why do we exalt objective reality, without any possibility of verifying its existence, and devalue the subjective, calling it an illusion, if this is all we have? Let us discard all the “what ifs” and focus on what truly exists: a multitude of elements arranged in subjective space without gaps. Each element possesses a set of qualities, the number of which may vary — this makes each one unique. Identical qualities may pertain to multiple elements, yet some are singular, applying only to one. An element without any qualities cannot exist, and yet these two concepts are not interchangeable. One can imagine qualities as extended layers forming the fabric of perception. If, in some part of subjective space, the fabric has a different structure — some layers are lost and/or new ones appear — the sense of difference allows us to treat it as something distinct. Yet this fabric is continuous: “emptiness” between elements is itself a quality; otherwise, we could not perceive it. Continuity, belonging, and uniqueness are the fundamental characteristics of all that is perceived.

Consider such an element: a cube made of an unknown material... but from what angle? And by what method? Observing it from one side, from experience, you know there are others. Confirm this again: walk around it or turn it over; now you no longer see the previous view. Forgot to check its size — take a ruler; weight — a scale; chemical composition — an XRF

analyzer: qualities we deem superior to others. And what about the atoms themselves that constitute it — what is their structure and nature? You cannot grasp all the cube's qualities at a glance, perhaps not even after the last, and with each new attempt to capture the remaining ones, the previous ones are lost — such is reality. “Is it truly impossible to preserve all its qualities, or at least those discovered, in texts or diagrams?” Can you perceive another's pain by hearing their cry? Faith, knowledge, opinion, doubt, thoughts, data from measuring devices — they are not bags carrying things; they are among the qualities laid upon them, like layers of paint. We do not run around something incompletely known, attempting to construct its full or true description; there is only what stands before us at the moment. The crumpled clothing on a chair, which in dim light you sincerely took for a frightening creature, was, unfortunately, that at the time. When you look closely and realize it was crumpled clothing, and the creature you saw was a pareidolic illusion — a moment for a new reality arrives. Even the potential to experience visual hallucinations while simultaneously being aware that it is not real does not imply that hallucinations are extraneous in subjective space. They are just as real an element as hallucinations without awareness, only now augmented with the latter as a quality, even if it is unusual to regard it as such.

What kept me from grasping all this for so long was a certain “point of reference” from which I look at all these things — the one I take to be “myself”. If everything around me, just as it is, belongs to me, to my subjective experience, why then is it observed as if from the outside? It seems that the invisibility of this “point” makes it central: you cannot turn toward it. Yet words flying out of the mouth cannot be followed by the eyes either, and still, they can be heard. Sound belongs to them, while invisibility — and my feelings — belong to “me”.

If what can be painful — feelings — belongs only to “me”, and to others belongs only my assumption that they, too, have them, does that mean I am entitled to do whatever I wish on my own territory?.. It is quite possible that a subjective world exists besides mine, and it most likely differs from it. Otherwise there would be no logic — two non-unique elements in terms of qualities and localization within the subjective spaces of two worlds should be ruled out. What if there is an infinite multitude of such worlds? It feels strange that the elements in my world are not infinite in number, and that here exist precisely these elements and not others.

But if we accept the principle of excluding non-unique elements, things become a little clearer: the number of randomly generated elements in any single world would be infinite if there were no neighboring ones. Infinities do not make anything possible because of randomness, yet it saves them from vanishing. ...So what about permissiveness? If in one world “you” make an unethical choice, randomness might play a nasty trick in another: it could place “you” in every possible position of subjective space except the original one. And in a third — “you” again, yet slightly altered, and possibly not to your advantage. Perhaps randomness is not a malevolent force, but merely a collectively made wrong choice.

It's time

A constant feeling of change: that something is no longer here, and something will come to take its place. A constant expectation, with every *next moment(?)*. All possible elements long ago took their places, as soon as they appeared out of nowhere — so do they still have somewhere to go?